

TABLE 1—BENZYLTHIURONIUM DITHIOCARBAMATES

Amine	Cor., m.p. of Salts	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen	
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
Ethanolamine	96	43.57	43.26	5.61	6.07	13.87	14.12
3-Propanolamine	91	45.42	45.78	5.99	5.81	13.24	13.30
Diethylamine	100	49.52	49.98	6.67	6.43	13.33	14.10

extensive decomposition of the liberated benzylisothiourea. In an essentially nonaqueous medium, the reaction of aliphatic amines with carbon disulfide to form dithiocarbamic acids² is approximately 90 to 95% complete. By using benzylthiuronium bicarbonate³ instead of benzylthiuronium chloride, the derivatization of aliphatic amines based on the following reaction can, therefore, be carried out with convenience.

The reagent has been observed to have a tendency to decompose at room temperature, however, a well dried sample is stable if stored in a refrigerator. The modified procedure does not require the adjustment of pH and affords better yields because the solid reagent is added till all the dithiocarbamic acid has reacted and the effervescence ceases. The modified procedure was tested in the case of all the aliphatic amines the derivatization of which was reported¹ earlier, the melting points of the derivatives thus obtained agree well with the reported values¹. The data regarding three more aliphatic amines, which have been derivatized now, is furnished in Table 1.

Experimental

Preparation of Benzylthiuronium Dithiocarbamates. In a 10 ml conical flask, 5 drops of an amine, 2 ml of ethanol and 0.5 ml of carbon disulfide are taken. The mixture is swirled for a few minutes and the reagent is added intermittently till the effervescence ceases. Benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates precipitate at room temperature in most cases, however, in some cases, refrigeration is necessary. The

precipitate is collected by suction filtration. Recrystallization from ethanol affords pure products. Prolonged heating during recrystallization should be avoided because it causes partial decomposition. The derivatives are dried in a vacuum desiccator and the melting points determined by the capillary tube method.

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An Electrochemical Technique for Preparation of Deionized Water

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IT was earlier reported by Palit¹ that electrolysis in W-tube cells results in formation of two sharp and static boundaries dividing the entire solution into three zones, viz., (i) cathodic alkaline, (ii) central neutral (water), and (iii) acidic anodic zones. A peculiar characteristic of the phenomenon is strong ion depletion in the central non-electrode zone. Later studies on theoretical aspects of this phenomenon² led to a deeper insight into the W-tube phenomena and experimental development of a much quicker method for producing the phenomenon, by induced ion-sweeping action of suitably added concentrated electrolytes (see Discussion). Further it has been recently reported by Palit that brisk ion-migration can occur even in trans-electrode regions during electrolysis³. Based on a combination of all these three principles we present here an

electrochemical deionization technique for preparation of water of conductivity water grade from ordinary tap water.

Experimental

A cell (vide Fig. 1) essentially of the W-tube type with large intermediate zone of 750 ml capacity is charged with ordinary tap water. Few ml of $\sim 10N$ H_2SO_4 and $\sim 10N$ $NaOH$ are added to the anode and cathode solutions respectively. The whole system is then electrolyzed using inert electrodes e.g., platinum, graphite etc. at 60 mA from a regulated D.C. power supply. About 100 volts are necessary to start with. The above cell design has the advantage in preventing the intermixing of solutions of its different compartments through diffusion and convection during electrolysis. A judicious choice of the experimental variables is essential to avoid

FIG. 1.

development of glow-electrolysis phenomenon⁴. The above electrolysis is allowed to continue for 48 hrs or so when the ammeter reading would fall to a figure around 1 mA. The clear liquid so formed in the central conical chamber is of specific conductivity 2×10^{-5} Siemens cm^{-1} at 20° (cf. specific conductivity of original tap water 5×10^{-3} Siemens cm^{-1} at 20°). In the next phase, this liquid in the central chamber is drawn off and transferred to another identical cell where it is electrolyzed without addition of acid and alkali at 300 volts for 24 hr or so at an average current of about 0.3 mA. The water so formed in the central chamber is taken out and collected. It has been found that by this process, water of specific conductivity 4×10^{-6} Siemens cm^{-1} (at 20°) as against the specific conductivity of double distilled water 6×10^{-6} Siemens cm^{-1} (at 20°) can be prepared. It is also of interest to note that total energy to be used for deionization of water by this new technique is about 0.9 times that for preparation of the same quantity of double distilled water by conventional technique. Here the typical results of preliminary experiments have been presented. Further work is

under progress to scale up the process for continuous preparation of much larger quantity of high grade deionized water.

Discussion

The deionization process described is based on the W-tube electrolysis technique introduced by Palit¹ and later theorised and further developed by Sengupta and Palit². During electrolysis of salt solutions in a W-tube, cathode and anode chambers get gradually enriched in alkali and acid respectively, upto the point where the boundaries finally develop. In course of such accumulation when the protons in the anodic section and hydroxyl ions in the cathodic section attain sufficient charge transport capacity, they migrate across the intermediate section in considerable proportion displacing out the ions of the electrolyte to the electrodic sections and finally form water there. It appears that the ions of electrolyte are as if being swept out of this intermediate region by the ions of the solvent. As expected the process has been found to be much accelerated, if at the start of the electrolysis the cathodic and anodic sections be made sufficiently enriched with high concentration of alkali and acid respectively.

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Action of some amines as corrosion inhibitor towards corrosion of 63/37 brass in potassium persulphate solutions

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POTASSIUM persulphate is a highly corrosive agent for metals and alloys; the rate of dissolution being of the order of 72 $g/m^2/day$.¹ Patel *et al.*²⁻⁵ also studied the corrosion of various types of brass and its inhibition in 0.2M $K_2S_2O_8$ solution. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the effect of some amines on the corrosion of 63/37 brass in 0.1M $K_2S_2O_8$ solution.

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